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Problem Dinoflagellates in Algoa Bay

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Contents

• Abstract.....	2
• Keywords.....	2
• Introduction.....	2
• Literature Review.....	5
• Methods and Materials.....	7
○ Study Sites.....	7
○ Sampling procedures.....	8
○ Cultures.....	9
○ Sediment samples.....	9
○ Identification method for dinoflagellate cysts.....	10
○ Vertical and horizontal tows.....	11
• Results.....	12
• Discussion.....	17
• Conclusion.....	21
• Acknowledgements.....	22
• References.....	22

Abstract

Dinoflagellate blooms, also known as red tides, are a worldwide phenomenon. The frequency of these blooms has been increasing in recent years and large dinoflagellate blooms have been seen in areas where they have not been previously recorded or if they have, the blooms have been a minor occurrence. Foreign dinoflagellate species are being transported around the world in a variety of unnatural ways. Among these are ballast water from ships as well as with animals for aquaculture. Bloom-forming and toxic dinoflagellates can be problematic. Red tides have significant negative effects on aquaculture as well as on the indigenous organisms from the area. Algoa Bay has two harbours, one of which is a deep water port. There are also two shellfish aquaculture farms in the Bay. The hypothesis for this project was that the oyster farming in Algoa Bay had brought in foreign dinoflagellate cysts and that such cysts would have sunk into the sediment at the time of seeding. The method for the identification of dinoflagellate cysts was to use cross polarizing filters on a microscope with the addition of a lambda plate. In all the sediment sampled from all the sites for the project only one dinoflagellate cyst was found. By contrast Bay waters had an abundance of cysts. So it seems that, in this case, the oyster farming has not brought in any foreign dinoflagellate cysts which could potentially be a problem for Algoa Bay.

Keywords: Dinoflagellates, cysts, cultures, identification, aquaculture, oysters

Introduction

Aquaculture is a growing industry and there are many different species being cultured (Pospelova and Kim, 2010). Often these commercially important species are not indigenous to the area that they are being grown in (Smit, 1993). This means that they have been brought in from another area and there is a possibility that they have brought other foreign organisms with them, such as foreign dinoflagellate cysts (Pospelova and Kim, 2010).

Dinoflagellate cysts are one of the biggest problems in terms of organisms that are transported to new areas. This is not only due to the fact that the dinoflagellates are exotic but also that they are bloom-forming and/or toxic, which then adds to the negative impact on the new environment that they are invading.

One of the biggest problems with dinoflagellate cysts is that they are very persistent (Brodie and Lewis, 2007). Cysts can survive very harsh conditions as well as remaining dormant for long periods of time. In this way, once cysts have been introduced into an area, they can remain there in this dormant state until the environmental conditions are optimal for them. They then germinate. This is also one of the reasons why it is very difficult to pinpoint the origin of a red tide. The species that is blooming may never been seen in the area before but the cysts of that species may have been present in the area for some time. Environmental conditions were simply not previously suitable for the cysts to germinate and a bloom to occur.

Another problem with long-lived dormant cysts is that they can survive for a very long time in harsh conditions, such as the ballast tanks of ships (Hallegraeff, 1998).

Dinoflagellate cysts do not need light or nutrients so they can survive long journeys that other, potentially invasive species would not survive (Smit, 1993).

Apart from having a comprehensive species list of the dinoflagellate species in an area, it is also very important to know what species of dinoflagellate cysts are present in the area. It is also important to know whether these cysts are planktonic or sedimentary and whether they are toxic or bloom-forming species. With this knowledge it will be much easier to predict what red tides could occur in an area and under what conditions the tide would occur. Not all species of dinoflagellates need the same environmental conditions to bloom (Ichimi et al., 2001). By monitoring the cyst species composition it will be easier to predict which species could bloom under future environmental scenarios.

Algoa Bay has had several aquaculture ventures. Many of these are no longer in use. There was a fin fish farm adjacent to the Port Elizabeth Harbour, but it is no longer operational. Oyster farming has also occurred here. An oyster farm was set up in the Swartkops Estuary, near the mouth, but those ponds are no longer in use. There is an active oyster farm north-west of the Port Elizabeth Harbour. This is a

fairly old, shallow water harbour. Algoa Bay also has a newer, deep water harbour at Coega. The shipping associated with these harbours could potentially be transporting and introducing dinoflagellates or other exotics into Algoa Bay.

Oyster farming has been occurring for many years and has caused many invasions of exotic organisms. On several local scales over the years the transport of oysters for aquaculture purposes has caused invasions of organisms including dinoflagellates that have rivalled the invasions caused by the transport of water in ships (Smit, 1993). In previous times oysters were transported as adults along with sediment. This sediment could be a rich source of dinoflagellate cysts and other biota which was then inadvertently introduced. Recently oysters have been transported as juveniles with the hopes of reducing the numbers of other organisms introduced with them.

Algoa Bay does not usually experience noteworthy red tides. However, the bloom forming dinoflagellate, *Noctiluca miliaris* Suriray, has been found in Algoa Bay and blooms of this species have occurred on several occasions in the bay over the years. However, these blooms are generally not on a very large scale. In January 2014, there was a large red-tide that reached from Algoa Bay eastwards up to East London and westwards down to Knysna. The dinoflagellate responsible for this bloom was *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (F. Stern) J.D. Dodge. This is a species of dinoflagellate that has not been seen in Algoa Bay before.

Thus, it can be seen that there are a few different ways in which dinoflagellates could be introduced into Algoa Bay. One of the major ways is through ballast water that is carried in ships. Another possible method is cyst transfer through aquaculture.

The aim of this project is to investigate the oyster farming operations as a possible source of problem dinoflagellates into the Algoa Bay area. The specific hypothesis for this project was that the oyster farming in Algoa Bay had brought in foreign dinoflagellate cysts. The main objective of this project was to test this hypothesis by examining water and sediment samples. Smit (1993) used microscopy with cross polarizing filters in order to locate and identifying dinoflagellate cysts and an additional objective of this project was to attempt to improve on this method.

Literature Review

The global transport of problem dinoflagellate species is problematic. There are many different proposed ways in which these species are thought to travel.

Dinoflagellate blooms, also known as red tides, are a worldwide phenomenon. The frequency of these blooms has been increasing in recent years and large dinoflagellate blooms are being seen in areas that previously they have not been seen in or if they have, the blooms have been a minor occurrence (Hallegraeff, 1993). The increase in the global occurrence of red tides has been hypothesized to be due to a combination of factors such as an increase in shipping and global climate change. When ships travel they carry bilge water and when they reach a harbour they release this water into the local ecosystem. This is a way in which dinoflagellate cysts travel and is one way that potentially problematic dinoflagellates are transported to new areas (Hallegraeff and Bolch, 1992). The dinoflagellates themselves die off during the trip but the larger problem is that their cysts lie dormant in the sediment picked up with the water. When the water and the sediment is pumped out of the ship again these cysts are released into a new area (Hallegraeff and Bolch, 1992, 1991). The cysts can remain dormant for long periods of time in the darkness of the ship and once discharged when the bilge is voided, they can stay dormant until conditions become suitable.

Climate change is affecting many aspects that in turn are influencing dinoflagellate blooms. The optimal conditions for red tides are warm, calm waters rich in nutrients. Whether or not a red tide forms is, obviously, not only determined by the local conditions but also by what species of dinoflagellates are present in the area.

Not all dinoflagellates form red tides. An example of a bloom-forming species of dinoflagellate is *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (F. Stern) J.D. Dodge (Gibson and Barnes, 2002). Among the bloom-forming species some produce toxins while others are non-toxic. However, a red tide does not have to be toxic to have detrimental effects on the ecosystem.

There are several different kinds of toxins that dinoflagellate species might produce. These toxins have different strengths as well as different effects (Turner and Tester, 1997). Filter feeders such as shellfish accumulate these toxins and this can lead to

illness and death for the consumers of the shellfish (Lee et al., 1989). There are four main types of shellfish poisoning: Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP), Neurotoxic Shellfish Poisoning (NSP), Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) and Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) (Falconer, 1993). Several different kinds of toxins of varying strengths may be involved in each type of poisoning. Yessotoxins are found in the dinoflagellates *Lingulodinium polyedrum* and *Protoceratium reticulatum* (Claparède & Lachmann) Bütschli (Paz et al., 2004). Yessotoxins fall into the broader group of DSP but there is some debate about whether the placement of this toxin is correct (Murata et al., 1987). There are several ill effects reported from the consumption of yessotoxins in large amounts. The debate about the placement of yessotoxins stems from the fact that they do not cause diarrhoea when consumed (Paz et al., 2004). The consumption of shellfish containing yessotoxins leads to myocardial lesions as well as changes to the heart muscle, liver and pancreas. If the bloom is dense enough or if the toxins in the bloom are strong enough it can also kill fish in the area. However, it is more common for fish and other sea life such as lobsters to die when the bloom decays and bacteria become so abundant that they deplete the oxygen in the water (Simon and Dauer, 1972).

Toxic blooms of dinoflagellates have a large and highly detrimental effect not only on the shellfish industry but also on some other forms of aquaculture and so need to be carefully monitored and well understood. Another common bloom-forming dinoflagellate is *Noctiluca miliaris*. This dinoflagellate is common in Algoa Bay as well as in many places around the world. While it often forms large blooms it does not produce toxins (Gomes et al., 2008).

Importing species for aquaculture can also bring in exotic species (Hallegraeff, 1993). Some cysts are planktonic and this means that they are transported with the sea water. Therefore, even if no sediment is transported with the organisms, invasive dinoflagellate species can be transferred. Many different species are used nowadays in aquaculture (Smit, 1993). Oyster farming has become a very large aquaculture industry along with several species of seaweeds. Mussels are also farmed commercially. Fish farming is also an ever growing aquaculture industry. Most of these species are not grown in the areas where they were originally found. This means that they are transported to new areas and when they are transported there is

always a possibility that sediment or water or even some of their associated biota travels with them to the new area. The organisms that travel with them can then cause problems in the new location. Oyster farming has been occurring for many years and has caused many invasions of exotic organisms. On several local scales over the years the transport of oysters for aquaculture purposes has caused invasions of organisms including dinoflagellates that have rivalled the invasions caused by the transport of water in ships (Smit, 1993).

Red tides can have devastating impacts on aquaculture ventures (Shumway, 1990). Unfortunately, aquaculture ventures can be responsible for bringing in invasive dinoflagellates into an area but invasive dinoflagellates can also be devastating for aquaculture projects. Dinoflagellate blooms can have a significant negative effect on aquaculture especially if the bloom is toxic. If a bloom is toxic it primarily affects filter feeding animals as they accumulate the toxins within them and this makes them toxic to whatever eats them (Crawford, 2003). Oyster and mussel farming are particularly affected. Red tides can also affect fish farming if they are toxic or when they begin to decompose and this causes anoxic conditions which suffocates the animals as they cannot simply move out of the area. Red tides can also affect seaweed farming. If the bloom is dense enough it can reduce light intensities sufficiently to have a negative impact on the growth of the seaweeds below.

Materials and Methods

Study Sites

Three study sites were chosen for this project. The first site was the oyster farm currently operating northeast of the Port Elizabeth harbour (Figure 1). The second and third sites chosen were the two old oyster ponds off the Swartkops Estuary (Figure 1). The oyster farm is currently in use while the two oyster ponds have not been used for the production of oysters for some time. All three of these sites are located within the Algoa Bay (Figure 1).

The oyster farm was sampled twice while each of the old oyster ponds was only sampled once. At all three sites sediment was collected for preservation as well as

for culturing. At the old oyster ponds water was also collected for culturing purposes and a tow net sample was collected at each of the ponds.

Water column samples were also taken from three sites in the Algoa Bay. These sites are part of the SAEON Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) programme, and are called S1, S2 and S8 (Figure 1). Tow nets (vertical and horizontal) were taken at these sites. Samples from January 2014 and June 2014 were examined.

Figure 1: The study area and sampling sites: the oyster farm just outside of the Port Elizabeth harbour ($33^{\circ} 56' 46''$ S $25^{\circ} 37' 32''$ E); the old oyster ponds off the Swartkops Estuary (pond 1: $33^{\circ} 52' 22''$ S $25^{\circ} 37' 36''$ E; and pond 2: $33^{\circ} 52' 13''$ S $25^{\circ} 37' 42''$ E); and, SAEON sites S1, S2 and S8 in the bay (co-ordinates for S1 are $33^{\circ} 53' 46''$ S $25^{\circ} 42' 8''$ E, for S2 are $33^{\circ} 49' 34''$ S $25^{\circ} 45' 15''$ E, and for S8 are $34^{\circ} 2' 3''$ S $25^{\circ} 43' 40''$ E).

Sampling procedures

Three sites were sampled. The oyster farm was sampled was on the 31 March 2014 and on the 11 June 2014. Each time 11 sediment cores were collected by divers at a depth of approximately 10 m, below the oyster lines. The sediment samples

collected were split and a portion used for culturing. The remainder was preserved in glutaraldehyde and kept for identification of dinoflagellate cysts.

Two disused oyster ponds were sampled. The southern pond (Oyster pond 1) was sampled on the 15 May 2014 and the northern one (Oyster pond 2) was sampled on the 04 June 2014. At each pond 11 sediment core samples were taken. The sediment collected was also used for culturing and some was preserved using glutaraldehyde and later examined for dinoflagellate cysts resting in the sediment. At each of the oyster ponds 6 water samples were taken which were used for culturing. A tow net (60 μm) was also used to sample the pond water and one graded sediment core sample was also taken from each pond. The graded sediment core samples were divided into five layers: 0-5; 5-10; 10-15; 15-20 and 20-25 cm. Both the tow net samples and the graded core samples were preserved using glutaraldehyde.

Cultures

All the glassware and seawater used for the cultures was autoclaved in order to sterilize it. Sediment and water samples were placed in sterilized Erlenmeyer flasks to which approximately 50 ml of autoclaved seawater was added along with 1 ml of Provasoli's and 0.1 ml of germanium dioxide (concentration 5 mg/l). The germanium dioxide was added in order to reduce the growth of diatoms in the cultures (Andersen, 2005).

The microalgae growing in the cultures were photographed using a Zeiss Axioplan microscope.

Sediment samples

Sediment samples were sieved, using a 106 μm sieve, to remove the larger sediment particles. Dinoflagellate cysts fall into the size range 20-100 μm . This means that the cysts would pass through the sieve. After sieving the "filtrate" was sonicated for 2 minutes in order to break up clumps and separate particles in order to facilitate viewing under a microscope. The samples were then allowed to settle for

an hour. Once the samples had settled a subsample was taken from the surface of the settled sediment and examined using a light microscope (Smit, 1993).

Identification method for dinoflagellate cysts

Dinoflagellate cysts can be difficult to locate in a sample using bright field microscopy (Figures 5a and 6a), especially when the cysts are buried in sediment. Even planktonic cysts can be hard to find with all the other particulates in the water. This difficulty motivated Reid and Boalch (1987) to research and develop an improved method for locating cysts. This method is based on the unique optical properties of the casing surrounding the cyst.

When cysts are viewed, using cross polarizing filters (crossed Nichols) on a polarizing light microscope, the cysts become significantly more noticeable. They glow and a characteristic cross shaped pattern is visible (Figure 5b). This cross resembles the interference figure produced by a uniaxial crystal (Reid and Boalch, 1987; Smit, 1993). A similar effect can also be seen with some armoured dinoflagellates (Figure 6b). In the case of dinoflagellates the effect is not as distinctive and the cross is less clear.

The Crossed Nichols method involves placing two polarizing filters on the microscope. The two filters are rotated so that they are orientated at an angle of 90° to each other. However, if there is a large amount of particulate material on the slide, the cross can be obscured. In this case the insertion of a lambda plate improves the effect. The combination of the cross polarizing filters and the lambda plate causes the dinoflagellate cysts to show up as having a cross pattern of blue and orange. The top left and bottom right corners appear blue and the top right and bottom left corners appear orange (Figure 5c). On a crowded slide this method makes the cysts to show up most clearly. This pattern and colouring can show up on things other than cysts (Figure 6c). However, it is generally quite easy to distinguish between cysts and the other objects (usually armoured dinoflagellates) which show this colouring pattern. Both the cross polarizing method and the lambda plate method work well at a range of magnifications including the lowest magnification of 40x.

Figure 5: Smooth dinoflagellate cyst at 200x magnification: (a) under ordinary light; (b) under polarized light showing a distinct cross; and (c) under polarized light and a lambda plate, showing negative uniaxial colours.

Figure 6: An armoured dinoflagellate at 200x magnification: (a) under bright field; (b) under polarized light; (c) under polarized light and a lambda plate, showing negative uniaxial colours.

The micrographs of dinoflagellates and dinoflagellate cysts were taken with a Leica DM EP microscope which had both the cross polarizing filters and a lambda plate.

Vertical and horizontal tows

The three horizontal tows as well as three vertical tows taken from the open water sites in Algoa Ba, were examined using the polarizing microscopy method as well as

the lambda plate method, to locate and identify cysts. These sites are S1, S2 and S8, which are being sampled as part of the SAEON Long Term Ecological (LTER) programme. These three sites were looked at in January (summer) 2014, when the extensive red tide bloom of *Lingulodinium polyedrum* was present in Algoa Bay and along the coast to the east and west, and then five months later in June (winter), by which time the red tide had completely dissipated.

Results

Cultures

No dinoflagellates grew in any of the cultures from any of the sites. Despite the germanium dioxide that was added a variety of diatoms grew.

Identification of dinoflagellate cysts

The dinoflagellate cysts were identifiable using microspore magnifications of as low as 40x (Figure 7 a-c). Both the methods - cross polarizing filters with or without the addition of the lambda plate – make the cysts show up clearly under this magnification (Figure 7 b-c). However, more details of the ordination of the outer wall of the cysts are visible when the lambda plate is added (Figure 7 c).

a

b

c

Figure 7: Dinoflagellate cysts at a magnification of 40x, (a) under normal light, (b) with cross polarizing filter, (c) with cross polarizing filters and the lambda plate.

Vertical and horizontal tow net samples

Dinoflagellate cysts were more common in the vertical than the horizontal tow net samples for January 2014. On average there were more than twice as many cysts in the vertical tows compared to the horizontal tows for that month (Table 1).

Table 1: The percentage of cysts to dinoflagellates found in the tow net samples at the three sites in January 2014.

Site	Vertical Tow	Horizontal Tow
S1	8.1%	5.2%
S2	30.0%	2.9%
S8	6.5%	10.3%
Average	14.9%	6.1%

For June 2014 the percentage of dinoflagellate cysts was, on average, the same for the vertical and horizontal tow net samples (Table 2) but was extremely low, less than 1%. The average percentage of dinoflagellate cysts (Table 2) was also far lower in June than in January (Table 1).

Table 2: The percentage of cysts to dinoflagellates found in the tow net samples at the three sites in June 2014.

Site	Vertical Tow	Horizontal Tow
S1	1%	0%
S2	1%	1%
S8	0%	1%
Average	0.7%	0.7%

The species composition of dinoflagellate cysts varied considerably between the two sampling dates. Five species were found in January 2014 (Figure 8 a-e) with the dominant one being *Lingulodinium polyedrum*. This was the species that was blooming at the time and the cause of the red tide. Five species of dinoflagellate cysts were also found in the June samples (Figure 9 a-e) which were taken after the bloom (red tide) had dissipated. Four of these five species were different to those found in January. The cyst shown in figure 8 b (Unknown cyst 1) was the only species found in both months. The June samples did not contain any *Lingulodinium polyedrum* cysts.

Figure 8: Species of dinoflagellate cysts found in the tow net samples at the three sites S1, S2 and S8 in January 2014: (a) *Lingulodinium polyedrum*; (b) Unknown cyst 1; (c) Unknown cyst 2; (d) Unknown cyst 3; (e) *Gonyaulax* sp.

Figure 9: Species of dinoflagellate cysts found in the tow net samples at the three sites S1, S2 and S8 in June 2014: (a) Unknown cyst 4; (b) Unknown cyst 1; (c) Unknown cyst 5; (d) Unknown cyst 6; (e) Unknown cyst 7

Oyster farm and pond samples

In the oyster farm sediments only one dinoflagellate cyst was found (Figure 10) but could not be identified. No dinoflagellate cysts were found in the sediments of the old oyster ponds.

No dinoflagellates were found in any of the sediment or water cultures that were done for the oyster farm or for those done for the oyster ponds. In both the tow net samples taken at the oyster ponds no dinoflagellates were found to be present.

Figure 10: The cyst found in the sediment of the oyster farm at 200x magnification: (a) under normal light; (b) with cross polarizing filters; (c) with cross polarizing filters and the lambda plate.

Discussion

Identification of dinoflagellate cysts

Dinoflagellate cysts are often very hard to identify in a sample, especially if it is a sediment sample or a dense sample from a red tide. Because of this different methods have been developed to identify dinoflagellate cysts under a microscope. The method used for this project was to use cross polarizing filters and the method was adjusted by adding the lambda plate to the cross polarizing filters to see if it improved the method (Reid and Boalch, 1987).

Both these methods worked extremely well for finding the dinoflagellate cysts in the samples. The addition of the lambda plate showed up more detail on the cyst than the cross polarizing filters alone. However, in order to identify the dinoflagellate cysts to species level they needed to be looked at under normal light on a microscope.

The cross polarizing filters on the microscope show up the dinoflagellate cysts because of the cross that forms on them. This cross looks like the uniaxial interference figure that appears on certain minerals under cross polarizing filters. Interference figures were originally used in mineralogy in order to identify what mineral was being looked at (Saggerson, 1986). There are two kinds of interference figures and these are uniaxial and biaxial interference figures. The type of interference figure that forms relates to what crystal system the mineral has. There

are seven crystal systems. These systems are cubic, tetragonal, hexagonal, trigonal, orthorhombic, monoclinic and triclinic. Those that fall into the cubic crystal system do not form an interference figure. These minerals are said to be isotropic and they appear dark under cross polarizing filters. Those minerals which are tetragonal, hexagonal and trigonal form uniaxial interference figures, while those which are orthorhombic, monoclinic or triclinic form biaxial interference figures. Interference figures can also be either positive or negative and this can be determined by inserting the lambda plate on the microscope. Whether an interference figure is positive or negative is determined by where the different colours of the sign lie in the figure. These figures are blue and yellow. In the case of uniaxial figures they are negative if the colours still form a cross with blue in the top left hand corner and in the bottom right hand corner, the yellow will be in the top right hand corner and the bottom left hand corner. If the figure is positive then the colours will be opposite with the blue in the top right hand corner and the bottom left hand corner and the yellow in the other corners. Biaxial figure can be determined to be positive or negative is almost the same manner. The only difference is that in biaxial figures when they are negative or positive a cross does not form. In the case of negative biaxial figures the blue colouring will be at the top left and the bottom right and the middle and the other corners will be yellow. When the sign is positive it will be the reverse with the yellow in those corners and the blue in the middle (Saggerson, 1986).

Dinoflagellate cysts do not actually form true uniaxial interference figures even though they appear that way. In fact the figures that form are biaxial and they are negative. This can be seen when the lambda plate is inserted. The figure that forms is actually biaxial because the layer of the cell wall surrounding the cyst is actually monoclinic or triclinic and this would cause a biaxial figure to form (Saggerson, 1986).

Dinoflagellate cysts have cell contents inside and they have three layers of a cell wall. They have an inner cell wall, a hyaline layer and an outer cell wall (Bravo and Figueroa, 2014). The hyaline layer is the layer responsible for the interference figure which forms under the cross polarizing filters (Reid and Boalch, 1987). The hyaline layer is composed of cellulose which has a monoclinic or triclinic crystal system.

The method used proved very good for locating cysts within a sample. However, the identification of these cysts proved very difficult due to their small size and the restrictions of the microscope used. The use of DNA sequencing in order to identify dinoflagellate cysts could prove very valuable (Kamikawa et al., 2007; Ki et al., 2005).

Vertical and horizontal tow net samples

The vertical and horizontal tow net samples taken from the three sites in the bay did not show much difference from site to site. The big differences were between the vertical and horizontal tow nets in January. In June the vertical and horizontal tow nets were very similar. The differences between the two months that were looked at were noticeable.

In January the vertical tow net samples had numbers of dinoflagellate cysts present more than twice as high as the numbers of cysts found in the horizontal tow net samples. This is most likely due to the dinoflagellate cysts sinking towards the sediment. If the dinoflagellate cysts are sinking as the data suggests then it would be expected that dinoflagellate cysts will be found in the sediments below these sites in the bay. In terms of future research, looking in these sediments for dinoflagellate cysts and seeing which of the dinoflagellate cysts found in the water column are in fact found in the sediments.

The vertical and horizontal tow net samples in June were almost identical. In both the tow nets very low numbers of dinoflagellate cysts were found. The composition of the species of cysts found in January and June very different and only one species of dinoflagellate cyst was found present in both months. In January cysts for *Lingulodinium polyedrum* and *Gonyaulax* sp. were found in the tow net samples. This was in the middle of the red tide which was mainly *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (Satta et al., 2013). It would make sense that during a red tide there would be mass encystment of the dominant red tide dinoflagellate species (Heiskanen, 1993). For both these species of cysts the motile dinoflagellate stage was found in the samples as well. In June neither of the dinoflagellate cyst species were present.

Oyster farm and pond samples

No dinoflagellate cysts were found in the sediment samples taken from the oyster ponds and only one dinoflagellate cyst was found in the sediment taken from the oyster farm. This would indicate that either there are very low numbers of dinoflagellate cysts in the sediment and the sampling method was not able to concentrate the cysts to a level where they could be detected or that there were no cysts in these sediments. If either reason is true then it suggests that the hypothesis was wrong and that the oyster farming in Algoa Bay has not been responsible for bringing in any foreign dinoflagellate cysts which are problematic.

The oyster farm outside of the Port Elizabeth Harbour does bring in their oyster stocks as juveniles and this does seem to have greatly reduced the transport of invasive organisms especially dinoflagellate cysts. Transporting the oyster stocks as juveniles is very advantageous in terms of limiting the transport of other organisms and in this way makes aquaculture a more environmentally friendly endeavor.

If practically no cysts were found in any of the sediments it makes sense that no dinoflagellate species were found in the sediment cultures. No dinoflagellate species were found in the water cultures either which suggests that no cysts were present in the water column either. The cultures were done in order to double check the method for finding the cysts in the sediment. From what was found it appears that the method for finding the cysts in the sediment does work it was simply that the cysts were only present in extremely low numbers if at all.

Even if the oysters were not responsible for bringing in dinoflagellate cysts it would still be expected that some dinoflagellate cysts would be found in the sediment below the oyster farm as dinoflagellate cysts would wash in from other areas in the bay and as the oyster farm is so close to the harbour cysts might be brought into the farm from there. It would appear that the density of oysters at the oyster farm is high enough that almost everything is filtered out of the water and in this way the dinoflagellate cysts are removed from the water before they can settle into the sediment.

Conclusion

Both the methods of identifying dinoflagellate cysts in sediments as well as water samples proved to be very effective. They were effective to very low microscope magnifications, working well to as low as x40 magnification. The addition of the lambda plate did show more of the ordination of the exterior of the dinoflagellate cyst. Both the cross polarizing filters and the addition of the lambda plate made the cysts easy to spot even if samples that were either full of sediment or with other organic matter. However, the best way to identify the dinoflagellate cysts to species level was with the normal light.

As no dinoflagellates were found in any of the cultures from either the oyster ponds or the oyster farm and only one cyst was found in the sediments from the oyster farm, no dinoflagellate cysts were found in the sediments from the oyster ponds, it can be concluded that the oyster farming has not brought any foreign dinoflagellate cysts into the Algoa Bay.

In the tow net samples from S1, S2 and S8 in the months of January and June the dinoflagellate cyst species composition varied greatly between these two months. No cysts of *Lingulodinium polyedrum* were found in June but many were found in January which was during the red tide. The *Lingulodinium polyedrum* cysts had either settled out into the sediment or had been washed away in the Agulhas current. Sediment below these sites would need to be sampled in order to determine if any of the dinoflagellate cyst species that were found in the tow net samples had settled out into the sediment. As there were many more cysts found in the vertical tows than the horizontal ones it suggests that the cysts were sinking and so at least some of them should have settled into the sediment in the bay. Only one species of dinoflagellate cyst was found in both of the months.

Since the evidence suggests that the aquaculture in the bay is not responsible for bringing in foreign dinoflagellate cysts the harbours in Algoa Bay should be sampled. Looking in the harbour sediments for dinoflagellate cysts in order to see if the ships are bring them in to the bay is important research that needs to be done.

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